

A Practice-Based Methodology for Capturing Embodied Gesture-Rhythm Relations in Small Datasets

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Abstract

This paper introduces a practice-centered methodology for building gesture and rhythmic phrase datasets to support music composition and performance. Rooted in individual investigations into gestural sensor use for sculpting rhythmic expression in electronic music, the approach integrates an improvisation analysis method developed by Rodrigo Constanzo with sound-tracing workflows. The resulting three-part dataset—comprising audio recordings, inertial measurement unit (IMU) and electromyogram (EMG) sensor data, and rich qualitative commentary—provides a flexible framework for merging embodied musical intuition with machine learning techniques. Positioned within the context of small-data AI, this work offers a nuanced, artist-centered contribution toward integrating qualitative and quantitative insights into ML-assisted systems for creative and expressive applications.

1 Introduction

While AI offers artists a plethora of new affordances, some artists struggle to balance the normative tendencies of ML with the subjective aspects of their practices, while others report a sense of disembodiment and shortcomings in communication with the model (Jourdan and Caramiaux, 2023). Simultaneously, there is an ongoing need for more practice-based research and feedback in ML for artistic applications. Creative practice often uncovers uses and challenges that enrich the design process, and keeping the “artist in the loop” during development helps ensure that resulting systems will respond to the needs of artists (Cavdir, 2024; Reed et al., 2024).

Gestural interfaces have a long-standing role in designing embodied interactions with computer-generated music, including the enhancement of expressive subtlety (Mainsbridge and Beilharz, 2014; Tanaka, 2009). Machine learning has also been used to assist in this process for some time (Visi and Tanaka, 2021), particularly via accessible tools like Wekinator (Fiebrink et al., 2009) and more recently the Fluid Corpus Manipulation (FluCoMa) library (Tremblay et al., 2021). However, there are many challenges artists encounter in designing effective mappings, from identifying expressive affordances appropriate for a given compositional strategy to documenting and working with movements which are instinctual and intuitive for the performer (Cook, 2017).

In my own (author one’s) practice, I have an ongoing interest in expressive timing in electronic music, partially influenced by a background in string instrument and percussion performance, along with experience in ensembles, from r&b to Balinese gamelan, where intentional timing variation is a core expressive tool. In conducting background research for new electronic music compositions exploring rhythm and timing variation, I was drawn to Vijay Iyer’s work investigating expressive microtiming as an embodied phenomenon (Iyer, 2002), along with the practices of artists like Laetitia Sonami and Atau Tanaka who harness movement and muscle sensing for embodied interaction with their musical material (Tanaka, 2009; Sonami, n.d.). I also became curious about the creative applications of insights and procedures from sound tracing research by Zbyszynski et al. and others, and the potential

for using ML as both a mapping and research tool for embodied musical associations (Zbyszyński et al., 2021; Françoise and Bevilacqua, 2018; Godøy et al., 2016).

2 Creative goals and primary contributions

Informed by these challenges and insights, I began investigating ways of applying gesture and machine learning research to my creative work with embodied rhythmic timing. However, in experimenting with mapping strategies and examining previous research, I found relatively little work on gesture and rhythm in practice, particularly in relation to timing variations and improvised phrasing. Because many of my creative questions centered around these relationships and correlations, I felt I could get useful insight for both mapping and composition purposes by investigating my own embodied knowledge.

To do so, I developed a custom analysis system to examine my own embodied gesture–rhythm associations, combining methods developed by Rodrigo Constanzo (2015) with the sound tracing methods referenced above. The output of this system is a dataset featuring three streams of information: 1) gesture sensor readings (from IMU and EMG), 2) recorded audio, and 3) rich qualitative commentary on my performances, all sharing the same time base to enable a variety of training, mapping, and analysis strategies. The goal is an approach to music information retrieval (MIR) that places the artist’s embodied practice at the center of the data, combines qualitative and quantitative insight, and contributes to small-data machine learning practice in the arts.

In the following sections, I will unpack this methodology in detail, providing concrete examples of how it draws from and influences my practice. Specifically, this paper presents:

- A methodology for building datasets for understanding artistic intention and embodied rhythmic knowledge, applicable to mapping, composition, machine learning, and embodied music research.
- An example of putting this into practice in an artist-centered, small-data machine learning workflow.

While this paper includes some discussion of machine learning, its primary aim is not to present or evaluate specific ML models. Rather, it focuses on a methodology for designing artist-centered datasets that support the exploration of embodied rhythm.

3 Related work and additional motivations

3.1 Prior work in gesture–ML for embodied music interaction

This research builds upon work by performers and researchers such as Laetitia Sonami and Atau Tanaka, who have developed nuanced technique and embodied knowledge via long-term creative practices with gesture and muscle sensors (Fiebrink and Sonami, 2020; Tanaka, 2009). Furthermore, it draws on the integration of movement and body sensor data with ML to investigate embodied musical associations and expressive subtlety (Caramiaux et al., 2015; Françoise and Bevilacqua, 2018; Zbyszyński et al., 2021). A core motivation of this research is to explore further techniques and expressive affordances available from these tools and methods, particularly in relation to rhythm.

3.2 Expansive definitions of rhythm and the role of embodiment

This paper uses an expansive definition of rhythm, covering everything from metered repetitive loops to non-metered percussive improvisations, the common factor being events distributed in time (Godøy, 2022). As a composer working with stretched time structures, I felt that movement and muscle sensors would offer interesting affordances in working with this definition of rhythm, particularly in regards to harnessing embodied rhythmic knowledge.

Rhythm is a deeply embodied phenomenon. According to Rolf Inge Godøy (2022), “Motor-mimetic cognition is concrete in projecting motor schemas onto sound, with motor features and sensations contributing to shaping images of sound.” My own performance experience supports this idea of embodied rhythm, as I often feel my expressive rhythmic decisions are guided by physically embedded

instincts, embodied metaphor, or learned cultural expressions performed by my body before I have time to think about them. In beginning to explore the use of sound-tracing and gesture data in my work, I was curious about drawing mapping strategies from this embedded body language.

3.3 Challenges in capturing embodied knowledge

An additional factor I sought to address within the design of this research was the fleeting and subjective nature of much of this embodied musical knowledge. In my experience, it is possible for an improvising performer to play a phrase that they'll never repeat again, or to vary their execution of a musical figure without knowing why they were doing it. For this project, I chose to capture data from spontaneous performances to gain insight into my musical language beyond my conscious intentions, or beyond what I might demonstrate when purposefully training a model by demonstration. I felt that such data would be useful for both analysis and mapping purposes in implementing an ML-assisted system with subtle, personalized expressive affordances.

4 Methodology

4.1 Research aims and dataset strategy

In pursuit of the above goals, I designed a system that would help me examine associations between gesture and rhythm in my own practice, while generating data useful in machine learning and embodied music research. I specifically looked for means to document expressive subtlety in real time, allowing me to learn more about my own expressive language while capturing data useful in applying these insights creatively. The result is an analysis system and three-part dataset structure harnessing audio, gesture data, and qualitative commentary. A common time base permits segmentation of any combination of this data to examine embodied rhythm for creative work, machine learning, or research purposes.

4.2 Related work on gesture mapping for rhythm

While much of the available research on gesture mapping focuses on sound synthesis and timbre, there is prior work applying such methods to rhythm. Waadeland (2011) used spectral analysis on musicians' body movements to draw connections between movement categories and rhythmic expression. Dahl (2014) investigated relevant movement features for triggering rhythmic events with air instruments. Scurto et al. (2021) tested an ML-assisted air-instrument based on drumsticks, enabling users to explore somatic relationships between movement and percussive sound. Gillick and Bamman (2021) tested a mapping by demonstration system using MIDI scores and performance examples to teach a generative rhythm model both what to play and how to play it. This paper adds to this body of research by examining gesture-rhythm mapping via personalized practice, along with a method for gathering rich, user-centric data for further research.

4.3 Influences on methodology

4.3.1 Mapping by demonstration and sound tracing

This approach draws particularly on mapping-by-demonstration and sound tracing methods, which examine users' gestural responses to audio stimuli (Zbyszyński et al., 2021). Sound tracing as a strategy dates back to the work of Becking and Truslit in the first half of the 20th century and has recently been employed with tablets and motion capture systems (Godøy et al., 2016). Françoise and Bevilacqua (2018) used IMU sensors and ML to examine correlations between gestures and vocalizations. Zbyszyński et al. (2021) employed ML in conjunction with sound tracing via multimodal gesture data to map users' gestural responses to pre-recorded sounds, delivering responses to later gesture performances via concatenative synthesis. Exploring the creative affordances of this research approach for small-data AI practice was a key motive for this project as a whole, and the method presented here draws on these technical strategies for constructing datasets.

4.3.2 Practice-based research approaches and Constanzo's analysis method

This project also builds on practice research as a methodology. Bulley and Sahin (2021) define practice research as “a type of research where practice is the significant method conveyed in a research output,” and it is often used to uncover embodied, tacit, or intuitive forms of knowledge that emerge through practice. Such forms of knowledge are a core part of music-making, but are also challenging to express in words, let alone numerical data. Within movement-based practice, Ben Spatz (2017) offers one solution via phenomenotechnical description, which includes using rich descriptive language to make their embodied technique explicit, replicable, and contestable by others. Researchers who harness creative practice in evaluating embodied interactions have also utilized approaches like autoethnography, interviewing, and thematic analysis to document the insights uncovered and identify common trends (Cavdir, 2024; Reed et al., 2024).

In seeking an appropriate practice-based methodology for this inquiry, I encountered an analytical method introduced by Rodrigo Constanzo in the 2010s, aimed at helping improvisers investigate decision-making during performances. Under this method, performers document improvisations using video and audio, subsequently leaving time-specific comments on their actions and intentions. These annotations are categorized into four streams—material, formal, interface, and interaction-based decisions—which can then undergo statistical analysis for deeper insights (Constanzo, 2015).

Although Constanzo's original method focuses on improvisational decisions, it is highly suitable for analyzing improvised gesture-phrase associations. For the present study, I adapted this method by removing the four decision streams and adding gesture data, thereby integrating qualitative commentary with quantitative insights.

4.3.3 Embodied rhythm and spontaneous performance

This approach was also influenced by research on rhythmic phrasing and its connection to body movement. Rolf Inge Godøy (2022) describes two phenomena related to embodied rhythm: rhythm objects, defined as “strongly coherent chunks of combined sound and body motion in music,” and coarticulation, “the fusion of motion events into more extended rhythm objects”. In his work on microtiming and embodiment, Vijay Iyer (2002) also links musical phrases of varying durations to corresponding body motions, ranging from moderate arm gestures to rapid finger movements. Research by Jensenius (2022), Visi and Tanaka (2021), and others has applied similar ideas within interactive systems. These notions about movement-phrase relationships influenced my application of Constanzo's method, particularly when analyzing my own performances and considering how to implement the resulting insights in practice.

Finally, as previously discussed, I placed a high priority on capturing spontaneous performance data through this methodology. Because the goal was to capture embodied knowledge and research intuitive mapping strategies, I wanted to reduce the role of premeditated gesture-phrase associations, and place my body in the lead as much as possible. In *The Primacy of Movement*, Maxine Sheets-Johnstone (2011) describes, “how moving is a way of knowing”. In discussing embodied mapping strategies, Jenn Kirby (n.d.) also suggests that we “let our bodies guide the interaction to understand the performative, expressive, and musical meaning of the interaction itself”. Capturing spontaneous movement data can also improve results for machine learning. As Zbyszyński et al. (2021) point out, musicians “often select the units with the most character” for mapping, leaving out more ordinary gestures. Capturing the full range of spontaneous movement fills in these gaps, contributing to a more realistic latent space representation and enabling well-rounded insights on embodied musicality.

5 Implementation

5.1 Overview of hybrid methodology

Informed by the influences outlined above, I built a hybrid method combining sound-tracing and gesture mapping techniques with Constanzo's analysis system, and implemented it in my own practice. To do this, I captured simultaneous gesture and audio data from a series of improvisations, then performed a qualitative analysis on the results, leaving detailed comments at specific time markers. A common time base for all data types enables training based on any combination of features within the dataset, while annotated time markers allow segmentation based on qualitative, performer-centric categories or values. The resulting data consists of audio files accompanied by

time-stamped commentary and sensor readings, with each set representing one short improvised performance.

5.2 Data collection procedure

To collect this data, I performed a series of rhythmic and gestural improvisations, with my left hand playing table-tapped rhythms and my right hand moving expressively to illustrate them. These rhythmic improvisations took the form of free-form phrases, without a fixed meter but incorporating percussive groupings and patterns with clear form and shape, somewhat reminiscent of the patterns of human speech or free-jazz improvisation. I aimed to move my right arm as if triggering the rhythmic patterns with the gesture sensors, seeking movements that felt intuitive in that context. I avoided thinking in advance about which movements corresponded to which rhythms, aiming to document subconscious embodied associations and allow a gestural language to emerge through action and repetition.

5.3 Technical setup and data capture

I documented these improvisations using a smartphone camera on a stand, taking video of the movements of my right arm along with audio from the table-tapped patterns to aid in qualitative analysis. Initially, I also recorded audio using a contact microphone taped to the table, but ultimately discarded these feeling that the room recordings had better timbral and dynamic range.

To capture gestural data, I initially sent gyroscope (x y z) and accelerometer (x y z) values to Max via OSC using the GyrOSC app from a second smartphone grasped in my right hand as I improvised. For later rounds, I also sent quaternion values (w x y z) from GyrOSC, and EMG signals from sensors placed on my right bicep brachii via the EAVI board and BBDMI library (Di Donato, Balandino et al., 2019; Di Maggio et al., 2023). All incoming data was compiled into a single vector in Max and recorded into a coll object at a regular sample rate (I experimented with intervals from 10 ms to 25 ms between readings).

While video and gesture sensor data were recorded separately, I built a Max patch to allow simultaneous visualization of the two forms of data after the fact (via multislidiers). This helped me to observe correlations between the two and verify that the setup was working properly.

5.4 Qualitative analysis and annotation

I recorded 26 improvisations over three sessions, each ranging between 15 seconds and 4 minutes in length. From these, I selected 13 for further analysis, occasionally choosing shorter fragments I considered particularly interesting. The dataset at this stage consisted of gesture sensor data and video files. To conduct my analyses, I temporarily placed the sensor data aside and uploaded the video files to Reaper, where audio files were automatically separated. I then followed a protocol similar to Constanzo's, placing time-specific comment markers on the audio files at relevant events while watching the videos.

My analyses included a high density of comments—often several per second—describing the movements I observed and their potential associations with the simultaneous rhythm performances. I used the onset time of gestures in the video rather than the audio to guide marker placement in order to document how my movements might precede or align with rhythmic events. To analyze especially intricate phrases, I sometimes slowed playback to half-speed. As common patterns emerged, I took note of these, and sometimes incorporated these emerging categories of movement into subsequent commentary. Similarly to Constanzo's (2015) analyses, my annotations combined descriptive, metaphorical, and technical observations.

6 Results

6.1 Final dataset structure

The outcome of this process was approximately 12.5 minutes of annotated audio, aligned with associated gestural data via millisecond-specific time markers. Each audio file is available in standard formats exportable from Reaper. Qualitative commentary is exportable as CSV files from Reaper,

Figure 1: Four screenshots of gesture improvisation video used for analysis. Right hand pictured holding smartphone with GyrOSC app, with EMG electrodes attached to the right bicep brachii.

Figure 2: Close-up of annotated audio in Reaper.

and gesture data as .txt files from Max, with both datasets indexed in milliseconds. Additionally, video recordings used to aid gestural improvisation analysis are available in .MOV format, enabling potential future analysis with motion capture systems (although such analysis lies beyond the scope of the present study). Samples of commentary and raw gesture data are provided below.

Table 1: Excerpt of time-stamped annotation of gesture performance

Start	Commentary
1:27.946	Clever/facile flicking motion
1:28.103	Up and down to indicate beats instead of moving side to side
1:28.907	Stop moving to indicate landing point (not a huge landing)
1:29.070	Also the start of a traced clock series. One phrase gives birth to another, which is why it ended that way?
1:30.008	End facing upward and lateral, pan-like movement
1:31.438	Leaning into the roll and sculpting it rather than illustrating each hit
1:31.816	Quick dip and upward flourish to illustrate sonic flourish
1:32.383	Come back down to upward-facing and incremental, jerky movements to illustrate sub-beats
1:32.963	Upward, open-handed movement to illustrate ending of phrase, empty space, waiting for next
1:35.159	Bring hand down to mean we're really waiting
1:36.889	Sudden eruption, but with a subtle roll like underneath a volcano. Not too sudden
1:37.494	Escalating to the sky via winding movements
1:37.615	Ends by metaphorically going beyond the range of the hand
1:38.787	Echo the upward movement for smaller phrase
1:39.378	Move downward to balance, wrap it up
1:39.773	Side to side wave indicates end of phrase/idea in a sense, clearing the air?

Due to a common time base, each data stream can be combined with any other, enabling the dataset to function as a flexible, unified multi-layer resource. Gesture data can be aligned with commentary,

(a) Gyroscope X, Y, Z

(b) Accelerometer X, Y, Z

(c) Quaternion W, X, Y, Z

Figure 3: Visualization of 500 ms of motion sensor data collected during gesture improvisation with the right arm, including gyroscope, accelerometer, and quaternion signals.

audio with gesture data, audio with commentary, or all three used simultaneously (or all four with the optional integration of video). This structure allows for rich analysis of performance tendencies for developing mapping strategies, advancing embodied music research, or refining personal performance techniques.

The dataset's flexibility also affords multiple approaches to machine learning, offering a range of possible combinations for training along with opportunities for segmentation based on audio features, sensor features, or qualitative commentary. Its grounding in my own artistic practice allows me to harness subjective embodied knowledge in applying the dataset, enabling iterative testing of its affordances within the rhythm- and gesture-based performance work I am currently developing.

In short, the resulting dataset provides a rich resource for investigating embodied gesture–rhythm associations, while demonstrating an MIR approach that merges qualitative and quantitative insights. It offers a range of possibilities for incorporating subjective aspects of artistic practice into small-data AI workflows.

Figure 4: EMG signal over 500 ms of gesture improvisation with the right arm (taken from same time slice as fig. 3).

7 Initial applications of the dataset approach in practice

7.1 Gesture–rhythm classification and insights

For my first investigations into using this dataset in my practice, I adopted a classification-based approach to the data gathered, revisiting my initial analyses to identify common trends within my performances. I found the dataset highly valuable for revealing correlations between rhythm and gesture in my practice, applicable to both traditional and ML-assisted mapping strategies. The process offered insights into my own embodied musical language that I would not have noticed otherwise, suggesting more intuitive and musically productive gesture–phrase relationships for performance system design and composition.

Several common trends emerged, including:

- Landing and pivot points: "Punctuation" points that subdivided or concluded rhythmic phrases, indicated by quick acceleration and sudden changes in gestural direction, and linked with strong rhythmic emphasis in the audio.
- Alternating and conducting movements: Broader sweeps of the hand and arm between pivot points, which seemed to shape the density, emphasis, and pacing of subtler rhythmic events occurring between more forceful rhythmic articulations.
- Anticipatory signals: Changes in movement that preceded significant changes in the audio, such as shifts in hand orientation, slowed rate of movement, and increased muscular tension.

I noted additional useful correlations, such as hand flourishes and quivering movements which mirrored rhythmic elaborations, and metaphorical gestures evoking specific rhythmic textures—ranging from imitations of household tasks to the dynamics of bodies of water or machinery. While a deeper exploration of these gesture–phrase associations would warrant a dedicated study (and has been pursued by other researchers), this preliminary investigation demonstrates the utility of this dataset approach for auto-analysis of one's embodied practice.

7.2 Mapping explorations and ML integration

Another significant advantage of this approach was access to audio and sensor data linked to specific gestural trends or patterns, easily identifiable through annotated commentary. I am currently testing classification and regression models on sensor features corresponding to several categories identified via the analysis to influence the behavior of audio and MIDI tracks in Max, utilizing FluCoMa's multilayer perceptron (MLP) objects. The results of these experiments, along with further creative applications of the dataset, will be reported in future papers and integrated into forthcoming performance work. It is important to note that, while these investigations are ongoing, the present study remains focused primarily on the development of the dataset and methodology within a practice-based context.

7.3 Reflections on embodied practice and creative potential

Beyond classification-based mapping scenarios, this dataset also provided rich insight into unexpected aspects of my embodied practice. In a manner reminiscent of Constanzo's original improvisation analysis technique, the process of conducting detailed annotation revealed subtle expressive variations and spontaneous decisions that would have been difficult to recognize otherwise (Constanzo, 2015). This was especially evident during the most intuitive, "in the zone" performances, where slight timing shifts and metaphorical movements emerged instinctively, carrying a palpable creative energy.

The commentary captured these moments, with the descriptive language offering a valuable resource for understanding and further developing these nuances. As a performer, having a multi-dimensional data trail for such fleeting, expressive instances was both illuminating and empowering. Although designing ML workflows for such highly variable, non-repetitive data presents inherent challenges, the thoroughness and flexibility of the documentation offer multiple productive pathways for creative exploration, research development, and system training.

In short, this detailed dataset provides a rich foundation for mining embodied musical insights over extended periods, reinforcing the potential for long-term artistic and research applications.

8 Discussion

8.1 Context of the method in small-data ML research

Although I developed this approach in the context of my own musical work, it is also intended as a contribution to discussions around small-data AI practice, and particularly the goal of putting the artist's embodied knowledge and intentions into the center of the process.

In a 2023 qualitative study on practitioners using ML in the NIME community, participants referenced a tension between the normative tendencies of ML and the subjective intentions of the artist, along with a sense of disembodiment in ML-assisted interactions (Jourdan and Caramiaux, 2023). This suggests a need for additional tools and methodologies to incorporate subjective and embodied insights into the training process.

One major challenge in this respect is translating qualitative insight from creative practitioners into actionable quantitative data. While we can translate body movement into numerical information via motion capture or gesture sensors, it is not so straightforward to incorporate the intentions and background knowledge that motivates and contextualizes those movements. This paper argues that practice research techniques are of valuable assistance here, and that finding new ways to place the artist in the loop in the research process improves outcomes for artists as end-users.

In a recent paper, Strauss and Yee-King (2023) explore a means of mapping embodied musical technique to a dimensional feature space, and argue that "our bodies are not a 'black box' of tacit knowledge". The method presented here offers a different but complimentary approach, supporting the argument that this tacit knowledge is explainable and harnessable, and offers important affordances for centering the artist within ML-based creative processes. By developing tools for this purpose within my own practice, I hope to contribute further useful pathways for harnessing embodied knowledge and subjective expressive language in building intuitive interactive systems.

8.2 Improvements on the system and future work

Improvements on this system for future research include integrating a glove-based IMU unit to allow free hand movement, testing a variety of EMG sensor placements, and taking higher quality audio recordings. To improve the analysis process, we are also considering using both start and end points for comment markers and integrating the complete workflow into Max to facilitate segmentation for training. We also hope to test this system with other musicians and their individual practices to provide more use cases for the system and collect feedback to refine it. We would be interested to see how this method could be adapted to different rhythm-based practices or alternate sensor placements.

From a creative standpoint, the insights from this research have already influenced the structure of an ML-enabled gesture performance system by the first author, to be premiered as part of a larger performance work in Fall 2025, and continue to influence ongoing composition work related to expressive timing.

9 Conclusion

In this paper, we have outlined a practice-based methodology for investigating gesture and rhythm, proposing a 3-layer data structure that merges qualitative and quantitative insights for creative, machine learning, and research applications. Our approach addresses the needs of small-data AI practice by offering a framework capable of capturing subjective, embodied insights in a form compatible with ML-assisted mapping strategies. It foregrounds the artist’s role in the dataset creation process, aligning data capture with artistic values, intentions, and embodied knowledge.

This methodology demonstrates how small, richly contextualized datasets can be systematically developed for AI integration while preserving artistic specificity. Although the study is based on a focused dataset within a single artistic context, the framework opens pathways for future expansion, adaptation to diverse practices, and further exploration of subjective mapping techniques in AI-enhanced creative workflows.

10 Ethics

This project is carried out using the authors’ own data, and all hardware and software used in our research is open-sourced, licensed, purchased, or used with the explicit permission of the developer. The authors also wish to assert that any use of the data collection methods described above should be implemented with respect for all participants’ data rights, including their consent to the use of their embodied data for research purposes. We do not condone using this approach to work with generative models trained on datasets which are not ethically sourced.

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